

A REVIEW STUDY ON THE COMPARISON OF *IKSHUMEHA* IN AYURVEDA AND MODERN MEDICAL CONCEPT

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ABSTRACT

Prameha is a significant disorder in Ayurveda, described in ancient texts with detailed causes, symptoms, and treatment. Classified as one of the eight major diseases (*Ashtamahagada*), it is closely linked to conditions like Diabetes Mellitus. Ayurveda describes 20 types of *Prameha*, with *Ikshumeha* being a specific *Kaphaja* type marked by excessive urination with a sweet, sugarcane-like taste. The study aims to explore the concept of *Ikshumeha* and its correlation with modern medical concepts, specifically Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. This study is a fundamental literary study analyzing *Ayurvedic Samhitas* and modern medical textbooks to establish a correlation. The observations of the study indicates a strong correlation between the Ayurvedic perspective of *Ikshumeha* and the modern clinical presentation of glycosuria in Diabetes Mellitus. This study concludes that *Ikshumeha* can be symptomatically and pathophysiologically correlated with

uncontrolled Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

KEYWORDS: *Ikshumeha*, *Prameha*, Diabetes Mellitus, Glycosuria.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the traditional system of medicine of India, highlights the maintenance of health through the balance of *Tridosha* (*Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*), proper functioning of *Dhatu*s (body tissues), and unobstructed flow within *Srotas* (body channels). According to Ayurvedic principles, disease occurs when this equilibrium is disturbed due to improper diet, lifestyle, and environmental factors, leading to pathological changes in the body.

According to the World Health Organization, Diabetes Mellitus is defined as a metabolic disorder with diverse causes, characterized primarily by chronic hyperglycemia. This condition involves significant disruptions in the metabolism of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins, arise from deficiencies in insulin secretion, impaired insulin action, or a combination of both.^[1] As of 2024–2026, approximately 589 million to 830 million adults (aged 20-79) globally are living with diabetes, representing about 1 in 9 adults. This number is projected to rise to over 853 millions by 2050.^[2]

Among the metabolic disorders described in Ayurveda, *Prameha* is considered as one of the eight major diseases (*Ashtamahagada*), it is closely linked to conditions like Diabetes Mellitus a major disease characterized by excessive and abnormal urination, turbidity of urine, and metabolic derangements.^[3] Classical Ayurvedic texts, there are 20 forms of *Prameha*: 10 are caused by *Kapha*, 6 result from *Pitta*, and 4 are caused by *Vata*.^[4] Etiological factors of *Prameha* are excessive intake of sweet (*madhur*), heavy (*heavy*), and unctuous foods, lack of physical activity, and hereditary predisposition.

The development of *Prameha* is closely linked with the concept of *Srotodushti*, which refers to dysfunction of body channels (*Srotas*) responsible for the transport of nutrients, wastes, and bodily fluids. When these channels become obstructed, dilated, or functionally impaired due to *Dosha* imbalance and accumulation of metabolic waste (*Ama*), normal physiological processes are disturbed, contributing to the manifestation of *Prameha*.

Among the various types of *Prameha*, *Ikshumeha* is a subtype in which the urine resembles sugarcane juice (*Ikshu Rasa*) in sweetness and appearance.^[5] It is generally associated with *Kapha* predominance and indicates severe derangement of metabolism. The understanding of *Ikshumeha* within the framework of *Srotodushti* provides valuable insight into the pathogenesis of metabolic disorders described in Ayurveda.

AIM:- To study the concept of *Ikshumeha* and its correlation with modern medical concepts, specifically Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All the Samhitas required for the fundamental literary study with available editions are as follows.

- 1) Charka Samhita - Nidanasthan 4, Chikitsasthan 6.
- 2) Sushrut Samhita- Nidanasthan 6.
- 3) Ashtanga Hridaya- Nidanasthan 10, Chikitsasthan 12.
- 4) Textbook of Medicine- Davidson's Principles & Practice of Medicine
- 5) Textbook of Pathology.

The research databases from various search engines, journals, *Ayurvedic Samhitas* and commentaries, and books were referred for recent information. Critical analysis of available literature was done.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

The following table provides a comparative analysis of *Ikshumeha* and Modern Medical concepts.

Table no 1: *Ikshumeha* vs. Modern Medicine (Diabetes Mellitus Type 2)

Feature	Ayurveda (<i>Ikshumeha</i>)	Modern Medicine (Diabetes Mellitus Type 2)
Definition	- Excessive urination with sweet taste (<i>Ikshu</i> = Sugarcane). ^[5] - One of the <i>Kaphaja Prameha</i> types, indicating metabolic dysfunction. ^[6]	- Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM): Chronic metabolic disorder characterized by high blood sugar levels (hyperglycemia) due to insulin resistance or deficiency. ^[14]
Causes	- Excessive intake of sweet, heavy, unctuous foods. ^[7] - Sedentary lifestyle. ^[7] - Impaired <i>Kapha & Meda Dhatu</i> (fat metabolism). ^[7] - Weak digestion (<i>Agnimandya</i>), leading to glucose accumulation.	- Obesity, poor diet (high sugar and fat intake), lack of exercise, genetic predisposition. ^[14] - Insulin resistance in muscle and fat cells, leading to high blood sugar. ^[14]
Symptoms	- Frequent urination (polyuria) with a sweet smell and honey-like texture. ^[5] - Increased thirst (polydipsia). - Fatigue, lethargy, excessive sweating. - Weight gain or obesity (<i>Kapha</i> dominance).	- Polyuria (frequent urination), polydipsia (excessive thirst), polyphagia (increased hunger). - Blurred vision, fatigue, slows wound healing. - Obesity (common in T2DM),

		insulin resistance. ^[14]
Pathophysiology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Kapha dosha</i> weakens <i>Medo Dhatu</i> (fat tissue) and <i>Mutravaha Srotas</i> (urinary system).^[6] - Excess glucose in the body is excreted through urine, making it sweet and sticky. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insulin resistance prevents glucose uptake into cells, causing hyperglycemia.^[14] - Kidneys excrete excess glucose, leading to sweet urine (glycosuria).^[14]
Treatment Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Kapha</i>-pacifying diet and lifestyle changes. - Detoxification therapies [<i>Panchakarma: Vamana</i> (medically induced vomiting), <i>Virechana</i> (therapeutic purgation), <i>Basti</i>(medicated enema)].^[8] - Herbal remedies to regulate sugar metabolism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blood sugar control through medications (Metformin, Insulin, SGLT2 inhibitors). - Dietary and lifestyle changes (low-carb diet, exercise).
Herbal Remedies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Shilajit</i> (Asphaltum Punjabinum)^[9], - <i>Guduchi</i> (Tinospora Cordifolia)^[10], - <i>Vijaysar</i> (Pterocarpus Marsupium)^[11], - <i>Karela</i> (Momardica Charantia)^[12], commonly known as bitter gourd), - <i>Jamun</i> (Syzygium Cumini, commonly known as Indian blackberry)^[13], - <i>Triphala</i>, Chandraprabha Vati. - <i>Guggulu</i> for fat metabolism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metformin, Insulin therapy (if needed), GLP-1 receptor agonists, SGLT2 inhibitors. - Dietary fiber, low glycemic index (GI) foods.

(SGLT2- Sodium Glucose Co-Transporter 2, GLP-1 – Glucagon –Like Peptide -1)

DISCUSSION

Ikshumeha is traditionally understood to result from an imbalance in *Kapha* dosha and the improper processing of *Meda Dhatu* (fat) and *Mutravaha Srotas* (urinary system). This reflects a systemic metabolic dysfunction leading to the excretion of abnormal substances—specifically sweetness—in the urine.

In modern medical science, this presentation aligns directly with Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 (T2DM). The *Madhurata* (sweetness) described in Ayurvedic texts is the clinical equivalent of Glycosuria, where the blood glucose level exceeds the renal threshold, causing sugar to spill into the urine.

Etiological Correlation: Both systems emphasize sedentary lifestyles and the overconsumption of *Guru* (heavy) or high-calorie foods as primary triggers.

Pathophysiological Resonances: The Ayurvedic concept of *Agnimandya* (weak digestion/metabolism) leading to glucose accumulation parallels the modern understanding of insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome.

Integrative Potential: While modern medicine focuses on pharmaceutical intervention and insulin sensitivity, Ayurveda offers a holistic approach through *Panchakarma* (detoxification) and specific herbs like *Vijaysar* and *Karela* which have known hypoglycemic properties.

CONCLUSION

From this review study, it is clear that *Ikshumeha* can be clinically correlated with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, particularly cases involving glycosuria. While Ayurveda attributes the condition to *Kapha-Meda* imbalance and metabolic waste accumulation, modern medicine links it to insulin resistance and renal glucose excretion. Bridging these traditional and modern perspectives allows for a more comprehensive approach to diagnosis and lifestyle-based management.

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